

Street-level weather station network in Freiburg, Germany: Station documentation

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Abstract

This report documents 42 stations of an urban street-level automatic weather station network in Freiburg, Germany installed and operated by the University of Freiburg and with support of the City of Freiburg and selected surrounding municipalities. The purpose of the network is to collect local and context-specific weather and climate data on temperature, humidity, precipitation and at selected stations also wind, solar radiation and black-globe temperature. This report documents all 42 stations with their position, address, land cover, orography as well as nearby objects that are relevant for the data interpretation. Maps are provided for each weather station detailing the location within the network, the local-scale siting, and the microscale surrounding. The report also documents mounting structures, sensors operated, operation periods and changes. Station photographs, panoramic images and sky-view images provide details on the siting and surroundings.

Keywords: Urban weather station network, automatic weather station, street-level weather station, meta-data, site documentation, Freiburg, Germany

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Network overview map

Abbreviations, definitions and measurement units

- **Coordinates** are given in decimal degrees (according to the Coordinate Reference System (CRS) WGS84).
- **Sensors deployed:**
 - o ClimaVue: ClimaVUE50 by Campbell Scientific Inc., Logan, UT, USA
 - o Pessl LoRain: Pessl LoRain (NBloT) by Pessl Instruments, Weiz, Austria
 - o Black Globe: BLACKGLOBE-L by Campbell Scientific Inc., Logan, UT, USA
- **Topographic elevation** refers to the ground level in meters above mean sea level and was extracted from a digital elevation model available at LGL¹ (CRS: ETRS89/UTM, spatial resolution: 1 m, creation date: 2000-2015).
- **Elevation above ground** refers to the vertical offset of the mounting structure base ground level from the surrounding ground level.
- **Local Climate Zones** refer to Stewart and Oke, 2012².
- **Urban Atlas Classes** refer to Montero et al, 2014³.
- **Center of mounting structure base** refers to the horizontal center of the respective pole at ground level.
- **x**: Horizontal distance in meters from center of mounting structure base.
- **z**: Vertical distance in meters from center of mounting structure base.
- **α** : Azimuth of respective object relative to mounting structure given in degrees (accuracy: approx. 20°).

External sources and tools

- Source of background for *aerial photographs*: LGL¹ (photographs taken in 2023).
- Source of background for *local-scale maps*: OSM⁵.
- Sky View factors were calculated from hemispherical photos at the location of the top of the Pessl LoRain or ClimaVue rain gauge, using the calculation method according to RayManPro⁶⁻¹⁰.
- All maps were created using QGIS⁴.

1: LGL, www.lgl-bw.de", use permitted under "Data licence Germany -attribution -Version 2.0".

2: Stewart, I.D., Oke, T.R., 2012. Local climate zones for urban temperature studies. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society* 93, 1879–1900.

3: Montero, E., Van Wolvelaer, J., Garzón, A., 2014. *The European Urban Atlas*. Springer Netherlands, Dordrecht. pp. 115–124.

4: QGIS.org (2023). QGIS Geographic Information System. Open Source Geospatial Foundation Project. <http://qgis.org>

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6: Matzarakis, A., Rutz, F., Mayer, H., 2007: Modelling Radiation fluxes in simple and complex environments - Application of the RayMan model. *International Journal of Biometeorology* 51, 323-334.

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9: Matzarakis, A., Gangwisch, M., Fröhlich, D., 2021: RayMan and SkyHelios Model. In: Palme, M., Salvati, A. (eds) *Urban Microclimate Modelling for Comfort and Energy Studies*. Springer, Cham., 339-361, https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-65421-4_16

10: Fröhlich, D., Gangwisch, M., Matzarakis, A., 2019: Effect of radiation and wind on thermal comfort in urban environments - Application of the RayMan and SkyHelios model. *Urban Climate* 27, 1-7.

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2212095518303225>

01 – FRASHA – Freiburg Alte Stadthalle

Station location and siting

Station ID	FRASHA	Full name	Freiburg Alte Stadthalle
Latitude	47.986557°N	Longitude	7.870209°E
Topographic elevation	296.0 m	Elevation above ground	0.3 m
Address	Schützenallee 43, 79102 Freiburg, Germany	Administrative unit	City of Freiburg, District of Wiehre
Local Climate Zone	6 (Open lowrise)	Urban Atlas Class	11210
Sky view factor	0.721	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Flat	Artificial heat sources	None
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	11 m	Parking space:	10 m
		Tree:	9 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Roughly E-W oriented street with boardwalk and interspersed parking spaces, 3-4 storey residential buildings with front gardens, street light pole located on low grass-covered mound (app. 0.3 m high), Hillside to the South at approx. 200 m distance.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey light pole	Material	Metal
Height of structure	6 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.1 m
		Light extension offset	0.4 m, $\alpha = 45^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base			
ClimaVue:	$x = 0.3$ m, $z = 3.17$ m, $\alpha = 230^\circ$	Black Globe:	$x = 0.38$ m, $z = 3.28$ m, $\alpha = 170^\circ$

History and remarks

History			Remarks
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-04-20	2022-08-10	Pessl LoRain	ClimaVue and Black Globe sensors experienced malfunctions from 2022-08-10 to 2022-09-27. No sensor was installed between 2023-03-10 and 2023-05-09.
2022-08-10	2022-09-27	ClimaVue + Black Globe	
2022-09-27	2022-11-10	Pessl LoRain	
2022-11-10	2023-03-10	ClimaVue + Black Globe	
2023-03-10	2023-05-09	None	
2023-05-09	-	ClimaVue + Black Globe	

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-02-21)

From East
(2024-02-21)

From South
(2024-02-21)

From West
(2024-02-21)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2024-02-21

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
Not available

02 – FRBETZ – Freiburg Betzenhausen

Station location and siting

Station ID	FRBETZ	Full name	Freiburg Betzenhausen
Latitude	48.0049°N	Longitude	7.817673°E
Topographic elevation	250.5 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Am Bischofskreuz 18, 79114 Freiburg, Germany	Administrative unit	City of Freiburg, District of Betzenhausen
Local Climate Zone	5 (Open midrise)	Urban Atlas Class	11210
Sky view factor	0.645	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Flat	Artificial heat sources	None
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	22 m	Parking space:	2 m
		Tree:	13 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
NE-SW oriented street with sidewalks and parking spaces on both sides, 6-8 storey residential buildings with large green areas and scattered trees between buildings.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey light pole		Material	Metal
Height of structure	9 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.12 m	Light extension offset 2.5 m, $\alpha = 145^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.42 m, z = 3.14 m, $\alpha = 190^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.38 m, z = 3.00 m, $\alpha = 220^\circ$

History and remarks

History			Remarks
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-04-07	-	Pessl LoRain	

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-03-05)

From East
(2024-03-05)

From South
(2024-03-05)

From West
(2024-03-05)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2024-02-02

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
Not available

03 – FRBRUH – Freiburg Bruehl

Station location and siting

Station ID	FRBRUH	Full name	Freiburg Bruehl
Latitude	48.031009°N	Longitude	7.854189°E
Topographic elevation	237.6 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Auerstraße 3, 79108 Freiburg, Germany	Administrative unit	City of Freiburg, District of Brühl
Local Climate Zone	8 (Large lowrise)	Urban Atlas Class	12100
Sky view factor	0.730	Dominant land use	Industrial
Orographic setting	Flat	Artificial heat sources	None
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	13 m	Parking space:	2 m
		Tree:	11 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
NE-SW oriented street with sidewalks on both sides and car parking on one side, light industrial buildings (halls) and parking lots.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey light pole		Material	Metal
Height of structure	10 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.12 m	Light extension offset 2 m, $\alpha = 140^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
ClimaVue:	x = 0.35 m, z = 3.25 m, $\alpha = 255^\circ$		Black Globe:	x = 0.40 m, z = 3.32 m, $\alpha = 185^\circ$

History and remarks

History			Remarks
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-04-05	2022-08-10	Pessl LoRain	
2022-08-10	-	ClimaVue + Black Globe	

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
Not available

From East
(2024-01-11)

From South
(2024-01-11)

From West
Not available

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2024-01-11

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
2024-01-11

04 – FRDIET – Freiburg Dietenbach

Station location and siting

Station ID	FRDIET	Full name	Freiburg Dietenbach
Latitude	48.013766°N	Longitude	7.792878°E
Topographic elevation	230.0 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Am Sender, 79111 Freiburg, Germany	Administrative unit	City of Freiburg, District of Rieselfeld
Local Climate Zone	D (Low plants)	Urban Atlas Class	13300
Sky view factor	0.868	Dominant land use	Agricultural / construction site (future city district)
Orographic setting	Flat	Artificial heat sources	None
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	None	Parking space:	None
		Tree:	25 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Meadows and agricultural fields, road, asphalted cycle path, transmission mast, ongoing construction work.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey pole		Material	Metal
Height of structure	3 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.06 m	Light extension offset None
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.12 m, z = 3.15 m, $\alpha = 55^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.08 m, z = 3.03 m, $\alpha = 180^\circ$

History and remarks

History			Remarks Station is in area of planned new city district "Dietenbach".
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-07-26	-	Pessl LoRain	

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2023-12-12)

From East
Not available

From South
(2023-12-12)

From West
(Not available)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2023-12-12

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
2023-12-12

05 – FRDREI – Freiburg Dreisam

Station location and siting

Station ID	FRDREI	Full name	Freiburg Dreisam
Latitude	47.995872°N	Longitude	7.826545°E
Topographic elevation	260.1 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Uferstraße 73, 79115 Freiburg, Germany	Administrative unit	City of Freiburg, District of Haslach
Local Climate Zone	6 (Open lowrise)	Urban Atlas Class	12220
Sky view factor	0.778	Dominant land use	Recreational/residential
Orographic setting	Inclined	Artificial heat sources	Cars (main road nearby)
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	31 m	Parking space:	50 m
		Tree:	52 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Small green stripe between bike lane and high-traffic road, Dreisam river at approx. 20 m distance (SE-NW orientation).			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey light pole		Material	Metal
Height of structure	5 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.1 m	Light extension offset 0.4 m, $\alpha = 25^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
ClimaVue:	x = 0.31 m, z = 3.00 m, $\alpha = 240^\circ$		Black Globe:	Not installed

History and remarks

History			Remarks
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-04-20	2022-08-10	Pessl LoRain	
2022-08-10	-	ClimaVue	

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-03-04)

From East
(2024-03-04)

From South
(2024-03-04)

From West
(2024-03-04)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2024-03-04

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
Not available

06 – FREBNE – Freiburg Ebnet

Station location and siting

Station ID	FREBNE	Full name	Freiburg Ebnet
Latitude	47.983431°N	Longitude	7.922671°E
Topographic elevation	340.3 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Not available	Administrative unit	City of Freiburg, District of Ebnet
Local Climate Zone	D (Low plants)	Urban Atlas Class	23000
Sky view factor	0.897	Dominant land use	Agricultural
Orographic setting	Flat	Artificial heat sources	None
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	None	Parking space:	None
		Tree:	None
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Flat grassland and agricultural fields, mound of 1.5 m height at app. 10 m distance (underground reservoir).			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey pole		Material	Aluminium
Height of structure	3 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.06 m	Light extension offset None
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
ClimaVue:	x = 0 m, z = 3.07 m, $\alpha = 0^\circ$ (on top of pole)		Black Globe:	x = 0.38 m, z = 2.71 m, $\alpha = 170^\circ$

History and remarks

History			Remarks
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-11-22	-	ClimaVue + Black Globe	

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-02-21)

From East
(2024-02-21)

From South
(2024-02-21)

From West
(2024-02-21)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2024-02-21

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
Not available

07 – FREICH – Freiburg Eichkopf

Station location and siting

Station ID	FREICH	Full name	Freiburg Eichkopf
Latitude	47.954049°N	Longitude	47.954049°E
Topographic elevation	694.8 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Sohlackerhütte, 79117 Freiburg, Germany	Administrative unit	City of Freiburg, District of Kappel
Local Climate Zone	A (dense trees)	Urban Atlas Class	31000
Sky view factor	0.687	Dominant land use	Forest
Orographic setting	Complex sloping	Artificial heat sources	None
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	None	Parking space:	None
		Tree:	4 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Clearing in the forest (mixed forest), meadow directly around the station, intersection of several hiking trails, small rest area for hikers with barbecue area; mountains to the Northeast and to the Southwest, sloping to the Southeast and Northwest, relatively steep gradient.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey pole	Material	Metal
Height of structure	3.09 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.06 m
		Light extension offset	None
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base			
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.12 m, z = 3.09 m, $\alpha = 115^\circ$	Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.08 m, z = 2.97 m, $\alpha = 240^\circ$

History and remarks

History			Remarks
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-04-13	-	Pessl LoRain	

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2023-12-12)

From East
Not available

From South
(2023-12-12)

From West
Not available

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2024-03-05

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
2023-12-12

08 – FRFRIE – Freiburg Hauptfriedhof

Station location and siting

Station ID	FRFRIE	Full name	Freiburg Hauptfriedhof
Latitude	48.010887°N	Longitude	7.841538°E
Topographic elevation	257.0 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Friedhofstraße 8, 79106 Freiburg, Germany	Administrative unit	City of Freiburg, District of Bruehl
Local Climate Zone	9 (Sparsely built)	Urban Atlas Class	14100
Sky view factor	0.762	Dominant land use	Cemetery
Orographic setting	Flat	Artificial heat sources	None
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	7 m	Parking space:	1 m
		Tree:	7 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Parking lot of a maintenance facility with a few buildings and a small garden located in a large cemetery with tall trees.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey light pole		Material	Metal
Height of structure	5 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.07 m	Light extension offset 0.4 m each, $\alpha = 150^\circ$ & 330° (two extensions)
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.39 m, z = 3.06 m, $\alpha = 30^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.35 m, z = 2.94 m, $\alpha = 60^\circ$

History and remarks

History			Remarks
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-04-05	-	Pessl LoRain	

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2023-12-01)

From East
Not available

From South
(2023-12-01)

From West
Not available

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2023-12-01

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
2023-12-01

09 – FRGART – Freiburg Gartenstadt

Station location and siting

Station ID	FRGART	Full name	Freiburg Gartenstadt
Latitude	47.986798°N	Longitude	7.824259°E
Topographic elevation	262.3 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Schenkendorfstraße 62, 79115 Freiburg, Germany	Administrative unit	City of Freiburg, District of Haslach
Local Climate Zone	6 (Open lowrise)	Urban Atlas Class	11220
Sky view factor	0.799	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Flat	Artificial heat sources	None
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	16 m	Parking space:	3 m
		Tree:	10 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
E-W oriented narrow street with car parking on one side and a narrow sidewalks on both sides, 3-storey residential row buildings, large gardens.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey light pole		Material	Metal
Height of structure	7 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.11 m	Light extension offset 0.5 m, $\alpha = 15^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.42 m, z = 3.10 m, $\alpha = 85^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.36 m, z = 2.98 m, $\alpha = 115^\circ$

History and remarks

History			Remarks
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-04-07	-	Pessl LoRain	

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-01-05)

From East
(2024-01-05)

From South
Not available

From West
Not available

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2024-01-05

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
2024-01-05

10 – FRGLBA – Freiburg Glasbach

Station location and siting

Station ID	FRGLBA	Full name	Freiburg Glasbach
Latitude	48.006918°N	Longitude	7.868736°E
Topographic elevation	289.5 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Jägerhäusleweg 26, 79104 Freiburg, Germany	Administrative unit	City of Freiburg, District of Herdern
Local Climate Zone	6 (Open lowrise)	Urban Atlas Class	11220
Sky view factor	0.475	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Slight slope	Artificial heat sources	Cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	6 m	Parking space:	1 m
		Tree:	10 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
NE-SW oriented small street, car parking to the side, narrow sidewalks on both sides, three-story detached houses, many hedges and gardens; slope rising to the North-East.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey light pole		Material	Metal
Height of structure	7 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.11 m	Light extension offset 0.4 m, $\alpha = 330^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.42 m, z = 3.03 m, $\alpha = 30^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.37 m, z = 2.91 m, $\alpha = 70^\circ$

History and remarks

History			Remarks
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-04-13	-	Pessl LoRain	Hedge underneath sensor between 2022 and 2024 growing closer to sensor.

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From Northeast
(2023-11-18)

From East
Not available

From South
Not available

From West
Not available

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
202X-XX-XX

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
2024-01-19

11 – FRGUNT – Freiburg Guenterstal

Station location and siting

Station ID	FRGUNT	Full name	Freiburg Guenterstal
Latitude	47.964012°N	Longitude	7.858853°E
Topographic elevation	339.2 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Dorfstraße 5, 79100 Freiburg, Germany	Administrative unit	City of Freiburg, District of Günterstal
Local Climate Zone	6 (Open lowrise)	Urban Atlas Class	11210
Sky view factor	0.620	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Slight slope inside valley	Artificial heat sources	Cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	8 m	Parking space:	1 m
		Tree:	20 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
NW-SE oriented narrow street with sidewalk on one side, 3-4 storey residential buildings, gardens, setting in a valley (mountains to the North-East and South-West).			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey light pole	Material	Metal
Height of structure	5 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.10 m
		Light extension offset	0.5 m, $\alpha = 230^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base			
ClimaVue:	x = 0.30 m, z = 3.22 m, $\alpha = 100^\circ$	Black Globe:	x = 0.39 m, z = 3.12 m, $\alpha = 185^\circ$

History and remarks

History			Remarks
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-04-20	2022-08-09	Pessl LoRain	
2022-08-09	-	ClimaVue + Black Globe	

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
Not available

From East
Not available

From South
(2024-01-05)

From West
(2024-01-05)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2024-01-05

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
2024-01-05

12 – FRHAID – Freiburg Haid

Station location and siting

Station ID	FRHAID	Full name	Freiburg Haid
Latitude	47.985761°N	Longitude	7.785271°E
Topographic elevation	235.4 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Burkheimer Straße 12, 79111 Freiburg, Germany	Administrative unit	City of Freiburg, District of Sankt Georgen
Local Climate Zone	8 (Large lowrise)	Urban Atlas Class	12100
Sky view factor	0.829	Dominant land use	Industrial
Orographic setting	Flat	Artificial heat sources	Cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	20 m	Parking space:	2 m
		Tree:	7 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
N-S oriented street with wide boardwalks and parking spaces, 1-2 storey light industrial / commercial buildings with parking lots and green stripes in front.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey light pole		Material	Metal
Height of structure	8 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.13 m	Light extension offset 3 m, $\alpha = 120^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.47 m, z = 3.13 m, $\alpha = 170^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.39 m, z = 3.01 m, $\alpha = 200^\circ$

History and remarks

History			Remarks
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-04-07	-	Pessl LoRain	

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-03-05)

From East
(2024-03-05)

From South
(2024-03-05)

From West
(2024-03-05)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2024-03-05

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
Not available

13 – FRHBHF – Freiburg Hauptbahnhof

Station location and siting

Station ID	FRHBHF	Full name	Freiburg Hauptbahnhof
Latitude	47.999806°N	Longitude	7.842381°E
Topographic elevation	271.1 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Lehener Straße 10, 79106 Freiburg, Germany	Administrative unit	City of Freiburg, District of Stühlinger
Local Climate Zone	5 (Open midrise)	Urban Atlas Class	12230
Sky view factor	0.689	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Flat	Artificial heat sources	None
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	10 m	Parking space:	10 m
		Tree:	18 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
E-W oriented street, 2-3 storey residential buildings, rail tracks of main station app. 50 m to the East.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey light pole		Material	Metal
Height of structure	7 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.12 m	Light extension offset 2 m, $\alpha = 205^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.43 m, z = 3.22 m, $\alpha = 290^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.36 m, z = 3.10 m, $\alpha = 320^\circ$

History and remarks

History			Remarks Heavy construction works under way since Jan. 2024.
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-04-05	-	Pessl LoRain	

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-03-04)

From East
(2024-03-04)

From South
(2024-03-04)

From West
(2024-03-04)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2024-03-04

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
Not available

14 – FRHERD – Freiburg Herdern

Station location and siting

Station ID	FRHERD	Full name	Freiburg Herdern
Latitude	48.006103°N	Longitude	7.856615°E
Topographic elevation	265.8 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Burgunder Straße 10, 79104 Freiburg, Germany	Administrative unit	City of Freiburg, District of Herdern
Local Climate Zone	6 (Open lowrise)	Urban Atlas Class	11210
Sky view factor	0.522	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Flat	Artificial heat sources	Cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	10 m	Parking space:	1 m
		Tree:	11 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
E-W oriented street with car parking to the side, four-story attached residential buildings, wide sidewalk on both sides of the street, small park about 15 m away, scattered young linden trees on both sides of the street.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey light pole		Material	Metal
Height of structure	6 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.10 m	Light extension offset 0.4 m, $\alpha = 355^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
ClimaVue: x = 0.26 m, z = 3.24 m, $\alpha = 220^\circ$		Black Globe: x = 0.34 m, z = 3.20 m, $\alpha = 185^\circ$		
HygroVue: x = 0.40 m, z = 3.20 m, $\alpha = 60^\circ$				

History and remarks

History			Remarks
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-04-13	2022-08-10	Pessl LoRain	Since 2023-08-14, the station is equipped with a HygroVue 10 sensor by Campbell Scientific in addition to the ClimaVue and Blackglobe sensors.
2022-08-10	2023-08-14	ClimaVue + Black Globe	
2023-08-14	-	ClimaVue + Black Globe+ HygroVue	

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2023-11-18)

From East
(2023-11-18)

From South
Not available

From West
Not available

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2023-11-18

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
2024-01-19

15 – FRHOCH – Freiburg Hochdorf

Station location and siting

Station ID	FRHOCH	Full name	Freiburg Hochdorf
Latitude	48.053762°N	Longitude	7.805014°E
Topographic elevation	226.8 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Benzhauser Straße, 79108 Freiburg, Germany	Administrative unit	City of Freiburg, District of Hochdorf
Local Climate Zone	D (Low plants)	Urban Atlas Class	21000
Sky view factor	0.875	Dominant land use	Agricultural
Orographic setting	Slight slope	Artificial heat sources	None
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	None	Parking space:	None
		Tree:	>50 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Agricultural fields, scattered trees, NE-SW oriented road, narrow sidewalk, surrounded slope rising to the South-East and the North-West and falling to the North-East and South-West.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey light pole		Material	Metal
Height of structure	10 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.10 m	Light extension offset 0.3 m, $\alpha = 295^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.43 m, z = 3.25 m, $\alpha = 145^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.39 m, z = 3.12 m, $\alpha = 175^\circ$

History and remarks

History			Remarks
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-04-05	-	Pessl LoRain	

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2023-12-12)

From East
(2023-12-12)

From South
Not available

From West
Not available

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2023-12-12

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
2023-12-12

16 – FRHOLZ – Freiburg Holzmarkt

Station location and siting

Station ID	FRHOLZ	Full name	Freiburg Holzmarkt
Latitude	47.990968°N	Longitude	7.850207°E
Topographic elevation	279.1 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Luisenstraße 9, 79098 Freiburg, Germany	Administrative unit	City of Freiburg, District of Altstadt
Local Climate Zone	5 (Open midrise)	Urban Atlas Class	11210
Sky view factor	0.632	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Flat	Artificial heat sources	Cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	6 m	Parking space:	1 m
		Tree:	6 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
N-S oriented street with car parking on both sides, wide sidewalks on both sides; trees on both sides of the road; 3-4 storey residential detached / semi-detached buildings with large, paved driveways, River Dreisam 100 m to the South.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Green light pole		Material	Metal
Height of structure	6 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.08 m	Light extension offset 1 m, $\alpha = 280^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.40 m, z = 3.10 m, $\alpha = 180^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.36 m, z = 2.98 m, $\alpha = 205^\circ$

History and remarks

History			Remarks
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-04-27	-	Pessl LoRain	

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2023-12-07)

From East
Not available

From South
(2023-12-07)

From West
Not available

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2024-01-19

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
2023-12-07

17 – FRIHOC – Freiburg Industriegebiet Hochdorf

Station location and siting

Station ID	FRIHOC	Full name	Freiburg Industriegebiet Hochdorf
Latitude	48.036945°N	Longitude	7.816336°E
Topographic elevation	223.0 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Bebelstraße 18, 79108 Freiburg, Germany	Administrative unit	City of Freiburg, District of Hochdorf
Local Climate Zone	8 (Large lowrise)	Urban Atlas Class	12100
Sky view factor	0.844	Dominant land use	Industrial
Orographic setting	Flat	Artificial heat sources	None
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	36 m	Parking space:	30 m
		Tree:	16 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Wide, N-S oriented street, boardwalk separated from street by 3 m wide grass stripe on which light pole is located, low light industrial buildings often with individual parking lots in front.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey light pole	Material	Metal
Height of structure	9 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.13 m
		Light extension offset	2 m, $\alpha = 50^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base			
Pessl rain bucket:	$x = 0.36$ m, $z = 3.16$ m, $\alpha = 150^\circ$	Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	$x = 0.42$ m, $z = 3.02$ m, $\alpha = 180^\circ$

History and remarks

History			Remarks
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-04-05	-	Pessl LoRain	

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-02-21)

From East
(2024-02-21)

From South
(2024-02-21)

From West
(2024-02-21)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2024-02-21

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
Not available

18 – FRINST – Freiburg Institutsviertel

Station location and siting

Station ID	FRINST	Full name	Freiburg Institutsviertel
Latitude	48.000045°N	Longitude	7.848589°E
Topographic elevation	274.2 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Rheinstraße 15, 79104 Freiburg, Germany	Administrative unit	City of Freiburg, District of Neuburg
Local Climate Zone	5 (Open midrise)	Urban Atlas Class	11210
Sky view factor	0.529	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Flat	Artificial heat sources	Cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	5 m	Parking space:	1 m
		Tree:	25 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
E-W oriented street with wide boardwalks and designated parking spaces, attached 3 storey residential and commercial buildings with scattered green spaces in-between.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey light pole		Material	Metal
Height of structure	6 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.08 m	Light extension offset 1 m, $\alpha = 120^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.35 m, z = 3.15 m, $\alpha = 255^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.31 m, z = 3.03 m, $\alpha = 285^\circ$

History and remarks

History			Remarks
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-03-30	-	Pessl LoRain	

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-03-05)

From East
(2024-03-05)

From South
(2024-03-05)

From West
(2024-03-05)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2024-01-19

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
2024-01-19

19 – FRKART – Freiburg Kartoffelmarkt

Station location and siting

Station ID	FRKART	Full name	Freiburg Kartoffelmarkt
Latitude	47.996988°N	Longitude	7.850794°E
Topographic elevation	279.3 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Schiffstraße 2, 79098 Freiburg, Germany	Administrative unit	City of Freiburg, District of Altstadt
Local Climate Zone	2 (Compact midrise)	Urban Atlas Class	11100
Sky view factor	0.270	Dominant land use	Commercial
Orographic setting	Flat	Artificial heat sources	None
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	2 m	Parking space:	None
		Tree:	None
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
NW-SE oriented inner-city shopping / commercial street in pedestrian zone with 4-5 storey attached buildings, essentially impermeable ground surfaces.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Dark grey light pole		Material	Metal
Height of structure	4 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.08 m	Light extension offset 0.4 m each, $\alpha = 110^\circ$ and 290° degrees (two extensions)
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.38 m, z = 3.38 m, $\alpha = 5^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.34 m, z = 3.25 m, $\alpha = 35^\circ$

History and remarks

History			Remarks
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-04-05	-	Pessl LoRain	

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-01-19)

From East
(2024-01-19)

From South
Not available

From West
(2024-01-19)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2024-01-19

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
2024-01-19

20 – FRLAND – Freiburg Landwasser

Station location and siting

Station ID	FRLAND	Full name	Freiburg Landwasser
Latitude	48.019458°N	Longitude	7.804825°E
Topographic elevation	234.2 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Eulenweg 11, 79110 Freiburg, Germany	Administrative unit	City of Freiburg, District of Landwasser
Local Climate Zone	5 (Open midrise)	Urban Atlas Class	11210
Sky view factor	0.701	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Flat	Artificial heat sources	Cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	7 m	Parking space:	2 m
		Tree:	17 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
N-S-oriented street with sidewalk on both sides, 1-2 storey row houses with front gardens, higher buildings in extended neighbourhood, patches of forest in proximity.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey light pole		Material	Metal
Height of structure	7 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.15 m	Light extension offset 0.4 m, $\alpha = 80^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
ClimaVue:	x = 0.33 m, z = 3.10 m, $\alpha = 230^\circ$		Black Globe:	x = 0.4 m, z = 3.20 m, $\alpha = 180^\circ$

History and remarks

History			Remarks
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-04-05	2022-08-10	Pessl LoRain	
2022-08-10	-	ClimaVue + Black Globe	

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-03-04)

From East
(2024-03-04)

From South
(2024-03-04)

From West
(2024-03-04)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2024-03-04

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
Not available

21 – FRLORE – Freiburg Loretto

Station location and siting

Station ID	FRLORE	Full name	Freiburg Loretto
Latitude	47.98118°N	Longitude	7.845321°E
Topographic elevation	281.2 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Silberbachstraße 15, 79100 Freiburg, Germany	Administrative unit	City of Freiburg, District of Wiehre
Local Climate Zone	6 (Open lowrise)	Urban Atlas Class	11210
Sky view factor	0.609	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Flat	Artificial heat sources	Cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	10 m	Parking space:	1 m
		Tree:	7 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
NW-SE oriented street with sidewalks, large trees, large detached residential buildings with 3-4 storeys and extensively vegetated front yards.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey light pole		Material	Metal
Height of structure	7 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.11 m	Light extension offset 0.5 m, $\alpha = 60^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.42 m, z = 3.13 m, $\alpha = 185^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.34 m, z = 2.99 m, $\alpha = 215^\circ$

History and remarks

History			Remarks
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-04-07	-	Pessl LoRain	

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
Not available

From East
(2024-01-05)

From South
(2024-01-05)

From West
Not available

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2024-01-05

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
2024-01-05

22 – FRMERZ – Freiburg Merzhausen

Station location and siting

Station ID	FRMERZ	Full name	Freiburg Merzhausen
Latitude	47.96012°N	Longitude	7.827334°E
Topographic elevation	311.5 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Near In der Ehrenmatte 44, 79249 Merzhausen, Germany	Administrative unit	Municipality of Merzhausen
Local Climate Zone	B (Scattered trees)	Urban Atlas Class	23000
Sky view factor	0.766	Dominant land use	Agricultural (Pastures)
Orographic setting	On a north-facing slope	Artificial heat sources	None
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	None	Parking space:	None
		Tree:	15 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Pastures, woodland and meadows, station is located on a dam with a temporary water reservoir (flood control) South of the station.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey light pole	Material	Metal
Height of structure	4.5 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.08 m
		Light extension offset	0.3 m, $\alpha = 205^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base			
ClimaVue:	x = 0.33 m, z = 3.17 m, $\alpha = 40^\circ$	Black Globe:	Not installed

History and remarks

History			Remarks
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-11-22	-	ClimaVue	Station features only ClimaVue sensor, no Black Globe.

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2023-12-12)

From East
(2023-12-12)

From South
Not available

From West
Not available

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2023-12-12

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
2023-12-12

23 – FRMESS – Freiburg Messe

Station location and siting

Station ID	FRMESS	Full name	Freiburg Messe
Latitude	48.01698°N	Longitude	7.842709°E
Topographic elevation	249.0 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Liebigstraße 23, 79108 Freiburg, Germany	Administrative unit	City of Freiburg, District of Bruehl
Local Climate Zone	8 (Large lowrise)	Urban Atlas Class	12100
Sky view factor	0.826	Dominant land use	Industrial
Orographic setting	Flat	Artificial heat sources	None
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	16 m	Parking space:	5 m
		Tree:	35 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
NE-SW oriented street with single sidewalk on the side of station, 1-2 storey detached industrial buildings with large parking spaces, high proportion of impervious / parved surfaces.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey light pole		Material	Metal
Height of structure	12 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.13 m	Light extension offset 2 m, $\alpha = 320^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.43 m, z = 3.20 m, $\alpha = 145^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.37 m, z = 3.07 m, $\alpha = 175^\circ$

History and remarks

History			Remarks
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-04-20	-	Pessl LoRain	

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2023-12-01)

From East
Not available

From South
Not available

From West
(2023-12-01)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2023-12-01

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
2024-03-05

24 – FROPFS – Freiburg Opfinger See

Station location and siting

Station ID	FROPFS	Full name	Freiburg Opfinger See
Latitude	48.01259 °N	Longitude	7.76453 °E
Topographic elevation	216.7 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Rehbrunnenweg, 79112 Freiburg, Germany	Administrative unit	City of Freiburg, District of Waltershofen
Local Climate Zone	G (Water)	Urban Atlas Class	50000
Sky view factor	0.716	Dominant land use	Lake
Orographic setting	Flat	Artificial heat sources	None
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	None	Parking space:	None
		Tree:	10 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Lakeshore and forest.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey pole		Material	Metal
Height of structure	3 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.06 m	Light extension offset None
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.14 m, z = 3.10 m, $\alpha = 40^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.9 m, z = 2.97 m, $\alpha = 140^\circ$

History and remarks

History			Remarks
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-07-26	-	Pessl LoRain	

Maps

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2023-12-12)

From East
Not available

From South
Not available

From West
(2023-12-12)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2023-12-12

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
2023-12-12

25 – FROWIE – Freiburg Oberwiehre

Station location and siting

Station ID	FROWIE	Full name	Freiburg Oberwiehre
Latitude	47.986906°N	Longitude	7.856149°E
Topographic elevation	284.1 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Landsknechtstraße 18, 79102 Freiburg, Germany	Administrative unit	City of Freiburg, District of Wiehre
Local Climate Zone	6 (Open lowrise)	Urban Atlas Class	11210
Sky view factor	0.479	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Flat	Artificial heat sources	Cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	7 m	Parking space:	0.5 m
		Tree:	6 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
N-S oriented street with boardwalk and trees, 4 storey detached and semi-detached residential buildings with front gardens.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Green light pole		Material	Metal
Height of structure	6 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.08 m	Light extension offset 1.2 m, $\alpha = 85^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.39 m, z = 3.11 m, $\alpha = 165^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.33 m, z = 2.98 m, $\alpha = 195^\circ$

History and remarks

History			Remarks
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-04-27	-	Pessl LoRain	

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-02-21)

From East
(2024-02-21)

From South
(2024-02-21)

From West
(2024-02-21)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2024-02-21

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
Not available

26 – FRPDAS – Freiburg Platz der Alten Synagoge

Station location and siting

Station ID	FRPDAS	Full name	Freiburg Platz der Alten Synagoge
Latitude	47.99516 °N	Longitude	7.845668 °E
Topographic elevation	279.3 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Platz der Alten Synagoge, 79098 Freiburg, Germany	Administrative unit	City of Freiburg, District of Altstadt
Local Climate Zone	5 (Open midrise)	Urban Atlas Class	12100
Sky view factor	0.677	Dominant land use	Recreational / commercial institutional (Square)
Orographic setting	Flat	Artificial heat sources	None
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	23 m	Parking space:	None
		Tree:	6 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
N-S oriented street in a pedestrian area, wide sidewalks on both sides, paved square / plaza to the East, large theatre building to the West. Usually highly frequented area.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey light pole		Material	Metal
Height of structure	10 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.14 m	Light extension offset 0.3 m, multiple light extensions in various directions
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
ClimaVue:	x = 0.36 m, z = 3.30 m, $\alpha = 235^\circ$		Black Globe:	x = 0.40 m, z = 3.38 m, $\alpha = 185^\circ$

History and remarks

History			Remarks
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-04-27	2022-08-10	Pessl LoRain	
2022-08-10	-	ClimaVue + Black Globe	

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
Not available

From East
(2023-12-07)

From South
Not available

From West
(2023-12-07)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2024-03-04

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
2023-12-07

27 – FRRIES – Freiburg Rieselfeld

Station location and siting

Station ID	FRRIES	Full name	Freiburg Rieselfeld
Latitude	47.998112°N	Longitude	7.79147°E
Topographic elevation	237.3 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Käthe-Kollwitz-Straße 14, 79100 Freiburg, Germany	Administrative unit	City of Freiburg, District of Rieselfeld
Local Climate Zone	6 (Open lowrise)	Urban Atlas Class	11100
Sky view factor	0.657	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Flat	Artificial heat sources	None
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	12 m	Parking space:	6 m
		Tree:	7 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Intersection, 4-5 storey residential buildings (some with front gardens), streets with parking spaces, boardwalks and narrow green stripes, sparse medium-height trees next to street.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Blue light pole		Material	Metal
Height of structure	6 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.1 m	Light extension offset 1 m, $\alpha = 300^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
ClimaVue: x = 0.32 m, z = 3.07 m, $\alpha = 135^\circ$		Black Globe: x = 0.29 m, z = 3.18 m, $\alpha = 190^\circ$		

History and remarks

History			Remarks
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-04-27	2022-08-09	Pessl LoRain	
2022-08-09	-	ClimaVue + Black Globe	

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-03-05)

From East
(2024-03-05)

From South
(2024-03-05)

From West
(2024-03-05)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2024-03-05

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
Not available

28 – FRSEEP – Freiburg Seepark

Station location and siting

Station ID	FRSEEP	Full name	Freiburg Seepark
Latitude	48.011264°N	Longitude	7.819404°E
Topographic elevation	248.0 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Not available	Administrative unit	City of Freiburg, District of Betzenhausen
Local Climate Zone	B (Scattered trees)	Urban Atlas Class	14100
Sky view factor	0.799	Dominant land use	Recreational (Urban park)
Orographic setting	Inclined	Artificial heat sources	None
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	60 m (Tower)	Parking space:	None
		Tree:	12 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Located in urban park with large green areas, scattered trees, vineyards and a lake at 25 m distance to the SW.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey pole		Material	Metal	
Height of structure	3 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.06 m	Light extension offset	None
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base					
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.14 m, z = 3.18 m, $\alpha = 190^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.10 m, z = 3.06 m, $\alpha = 315^\circ$	

History and remarks

History			Remarks
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-07-26	2023-04-18	Pessl LoRain	Prior to 2023-07-05, the station was installed at the coordinates Lat: 48.010896, Lon: 7.820641.
2023-04-18	2023-07-05	No sensor installed	
2023-07-05	-	Pessl LoRain	

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-02-02)

From East
(2024-02-02)

From South
Not available

From West
(2024-02-02)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2024-02-02

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
Not available

29 – FRSTGA – Freiburg Stadtgarten

Station location and siting

Station ID	FRSTGA	Full name	Freiburg Stadtgarten
Latitude	47.99782°N	Longitude	7.857968°E
Topographic elevation	278.7 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Jacob-Burckhardt-Straße/Leopoldring 79098 Freiburg, Germany	Administrative unit	City of Freiburg, District of Neuburg
Local Climate Zone	B (Scattered trees)	Urban Atlas Class	14100
Sky view factor	0.780	Dominant land use	Recreational (urban park)
Orographic setting	Flat	Artificial heat sources	None
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	14 m	Parking space:	50 m
		Tree:	8 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Urban park with mainly grass areas and scattered trees, asphalted paths and patches in between, small open stage South of the station; at the foot of a hill approx. 200 m to the East.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey light pole		Material	Metal
Height of structure	3.5 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.06 m	Light extension offset 0.3 m, $\alpha = 250^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.33 m, z = 3.30 m, $\alpha = 145^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.30 m, z = 3.18 m, $\alpha = 175^\circ$

History and remarks

History			Remarks
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-04-05	-	Pessl LoRain	

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2023-12-07)

From East
Not available

From South
(2023-12-07)

From West
Not available

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2024-01-19

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
2023-12-07

30 – FRSTGE – Freiburg Sankt Georgen

Station location and siting

Station ID	FRSTGE	Full name	Freiburg Sankt Georgen
Latitude	47.98025°N	Longitude	7.799452°E
Topographic elevation	243.9 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Salzburger Weg 13, 79111 Freiburg, Germany	Administrative unit	City of Freiburg, District of Sankt Georgen
Local Climate Zone	6 (Open lowrise)	Urban Atlas Class	11210
Sky view factor	0.682	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Flat	Artificial heat sources	Cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	7 m	Parking space:	2 m
		Tree:	7 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
N-S oriented street with boardwalk, 2-3 storey residential buildings with front gardens.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey light pole		Material	Metal
Height of structure	5 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.10 m	Light extension offset 0.4 m, $\alpha = 260^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.43 m, z = 3.07 m, $\alpha = 180^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.35 m, z = 3.07 m, $\alpha = 210^\circ$

History and remarks

History			Remarks
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-04-07	-	Pessl LoRain	

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-03-04)

From East
(2024-03-04)

From South
(2024-03-04)

From West
(2024-03-04)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2024-03-04

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
Not available

31 – FRSTUH – Freiburg Stuehlinger

Station location and siting

Station ID	FRSTUH	Full name	Freiburg Stuehlinger
Latitude	47.995906°N	Longitude	7.835886°E
Topographic elevation	269.4 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Grete-Borgmann-Straße 16, 79106 Freiburg, Germany	Administrative unit	City of Freiburg, District of Stühlinger
Local Climate Zone	5 (Open midrise)	Urban Atlas Class	11100
Sky view factor	0.345	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Flat	Artificial heat sources	Cars, buildings
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	3 m	Parking space:	0 m
		Tree:	90 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
NE-SW oriented narrow street canyon with parking spaces and boardwalks on both sides, 3-4 storey attached residential buildings.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey light pole		Material	Metal
Height of structure	7 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.15 m	Light extension offset 0.4 m, $\alpha = 110^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.42 m, z = 3.11 m, $\alpha = 190^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.36 m, z = 2.98 m, $\alpha = 210^\circ$

History and remarks

History			Remarks
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-04-05	-	Pessl LoRain	

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-02-02)

From East
Not available

From South
(2024-02-02)

From West
Not available

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2024-02-02

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
Not available

32 – FRTECH – Freiburg Technische Fakultät

Station location and siting

Station ID	FRTECH	Full name	Freiburg Technische Fakultät
Latitude	48.01529°N	Longitude	7.829959°E
Topographic elevation	247.2 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Georges-Köhler-Allee 73, 79110 Freiburg, Germany	Administrative unit	City of Freiburg, District of Brühl
Local Climate Zone	6 (Open lowrise)	Urban Atlas Class	11230
Sky view factor	0.862	Dominant land use	Institutional
Orographic setting	Flat	Artificial heat sources	None
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	7 m	Parking space:	10 m
		Tree:	5 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Located on green area (app. 10 x 20 m) with grass, sparse shrubs and small trees, rail tracks at approx. 50 m distance, metal bike shed at approx. 7 m distance, surrounded by grassland, parking spaces and university research facilities.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey pole		Material	Aluminium	
Height of structure	3 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.06 m	Light extension offset	None
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base					
ClimaVue:	x = 0 m, z = 3.17 m, $\alpha = 0^\circ$ (on top of pole)		Black Globe:	Not installed	

History and remarks

History			Remarks
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-11-22	-	ClimaVue	Incomplete data due to sensor and data transmission malfunctioning.

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-03-04)

From East
(2024-03-04)

From South
(2024-03-04)

From West
(2024-03-04)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2024-03-04

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
Not available

33 – FRTIEN – Freiburg Tiengen

Station location and siting

Station ID	FRTIEN	Full name	Freiburg Tiengen
Latitude	47.98153°N	Longitude	7.723827°E
Topographic elevation	210.8 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Freiburger Landstraße, 79112 Freiburg, Germany	Administrative unit	City of Freiburg, District of Tiengen
Local Climate Zone	D (Low plants)	Urban Atlas Class	21000
Sky view factor	0.838	Dominant land use	Agricultural
Orographic setting	Flat	Artificial heat sources	None
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	None	Parking space:	None
		Tree:	35 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
E-W oriented road with adjacent asphalted cycle path, surrounded by agricultural fields, high-voltage power line overhead.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey light pole		Material	Metal
Height of structure	4.5 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.09 m	Light extension offset 0.3 m, $\alpha = 35^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
ClimaVue:	x = 0.30 m, z = 3.40 m, $\alpha = 125^\circ$		Black Globe:	x = 0.37 m, z = 3.50 m, $\alpha = 180^\circ$

History and remarks

History			Remarks
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-08-10	-	ClimaVue + Black Globe	

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2023-12-12)

From East
Not available

From South
(2023-12-12)

From West
Not available

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2023-12-12

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
2023-12-12

34 – FRUNIK – Freiburg Uniklinik

Station location and siting

Station ID	FRUNIK	Full name	Freiburg Uniklinik
Latitude	48.005184°N	Longitude	7.839931°E
Topographic elevation	263.5 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Hugstetter Straße 55, 79106 Freiburg, Germany	Administrative unit	City of Freiburg, District of Stühlinger
Local Climate Zone	5 (Open midrise)	Urban Atlas Class	11210
Sky view factor	0.694	Dominant land use	Institutional (hospital)
Orographic setting	Flat	Artificial heat sources	Cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	10 m	Parking space:	5 m
		Tree:	3 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
SE-NW oriented street with wide boardwalks, designated parking spaces and scattered trees, 3-5 storey buildings (university hospital), small park at approx. 100 m distance.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey light pole		Material	Metal
Height of structure	10 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.14 m	Light extension offset 2.2 m, $\alpha = 220^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.42 m, z = 3.22 m, $\alpha = 110^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.38 m, z = 3.10 m, $\alpha = 140^\circ$

History and remarks

History			Remarks
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-04-05	-	Pessl LoRain	

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-02-02)

From East
(2024-02-02)

From South
(2024-02-02)

From West
(2024-02-02)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2024-02-02

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
Not available

35 – FRUWIE – Freiburg Unterwiehre

Station location and siting

Station ID	FRUWIE	Full name	Freiburg Unterwiehre
Latitude	47.98852°N	Longitude	7.842559°E
Topographic elevation	272.4 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Schwimmbadstraße 8, 79100 Freiburg, Germany	Administrative unit	City of Freiburg, District of Wiehre
Local Climate Zone	5 (Open midrise)	Urban Atlas Class	11220
Sky view factor	0.476	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Flat	Artificial heat sources	Cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	8 m	Parking space:	1 m
		Tree:	8 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
N-S oriented street with mature deciduous trees. Sidewalks on both sides and curbside car parking, 3-4 storey residential buildings with paved driveways and vegetated front gardens.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey light pole		Material	Metal
Height of structure	11 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.13 m	Light extension offset 2.5 m, $\alpha = 275^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.44 m, z = 3.16 m, $\alpha = 165^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.37 m, z = 3.03 m, $\alpha = 195^\circ$

History and remarks

History			Remarks
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-04-07	-	Pessl LoRain	

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
Not available

From East
Not available

From South
(2024-01-05)

From West
(2024-01-05)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2024-01-05

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
2024-01-05

36 – FRVAUB – Freiburg Vauban

Station location and siting

Station ID	FRVAUB	Full name	Freiburg Vauban
Latitude	47.976285°N	Longitude	7.823044°E
Topographic elevation	258.7 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Ida-Kerkovius-Straße 14, 79100 Freiburg, Germany	Administrative unit	City of Freiburg, District of Vauban
Local Climate Zone	6 (Open lowrise)	Urban Atlas Class	11210
Sky view factor	0.580	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Flat	Artificial heat sources	None
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	3 m (bike shed) 9 m (house)	Parking space:	50 m
		Tree:	4 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
N-S oriented pedestrian / bicycle lane (no cars), 4 storey residential attached buildings, front gardens.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Blue light pole	Material	Metal
Height of structure	7 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.07 m
		Light extension offset	1.2 m, $\alpha = 95^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base			
ClimaVue:	x = 0.29 m, z = 3.14 m, $\alpha = 125^\circ$	Black Globe:	x = 0.37 m, z = 3.18 m, $\alpha = 180^\circ$

History and remarks

History			Remarks
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-04-27	2022-08-09	Pessl LoRain	ClimaVue and Blackglobe Sensors experienced malfunctions from 2022-08-09 to 2022-09-27.
2022-08-09	2022-09-27	ClimaVue + Black Globe	
2022-09-27	2022-11-10	Pessl LoRain	
2022-11-10	-	ClimaVue + Black Globe	

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-02-21)

From East
(2024-02-21)

From South
(2024-02-21)

From West
(2024-02-21)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2024-02-21

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
Not available

37 – FRWAHS – Freiburg Waldhaus

Station location and siting

Station ID	FRWAHS	Full name	Freiburg Waldhaus
Latitude	47.970834°N	Longitude	7.84042°E
Topographic elevation	324.1 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Not available	Administrative unit	City of Freiburg, District of Günterstal
Local Climate Zone	A (Dense trees)	Urban Atlas Class	31000
Sky view factor	0.656	Dominant land use	Forestry/recreational
Orographic setting	Inclined	Artificial heat sources	None
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	4 m (Wooden shelter)	Parking space:	None
		Tree:	20 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Located on small forest clearing, consisting of grass, shrubs, educational garden and scattered small trees (Height < 5 m), surrounded by forest in all directions.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey pole		Material	Aluminium
Height of structure	2.97 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.06 m	Light extension offset None
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.12 m, z = 3.01 m, $\alpha = 45^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.08 m, z = 2.91 m, $\alpha = 170^\circ$

History and remarks

History			Remarks
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-04-06	-	Pessl LoRain	

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-02-21)

From East
(2024-02-21)

From South
(2024-02-21)

From West
(2024-02-21)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2024-03-05

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
Not available

38 – FRWEIN – Freiburg Weingarten

Station location and siting

Station ID	FRWEIN	Full name	Freiburg Weingarten
Latitude	47.995228°N	Longitude	7.807998°E
Topographic elevation	247.8 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Sulzburger Straße 5, 79114 Freiburg, Germany	Administrative unit	City of Freiburg, District of Weingarten
Local Climate Zone	4 (Open highrise)	Urban Atlas Class	11210
Sky view factor	0.645	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Flat	Artificial heat sources	Cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	39 m	Parking space:	0 m
		Tree:	11 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
N-S oriented street with sidewalks and parking spaces on both sides, 7-8 storey residential buildings with large, park-like green areas in-between.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey light pole		Material	Metal
Height of structure	8 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.13 m	Light extension offset 2 m, $\alpha = 80^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.42 m, z = 3.08 m, $\alpha = 155^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.38 m, z = 2.96 m, $\alpha = 185^\circ$

History and remarks

History			Remarks
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-04-07	-	Pessl LoRain	

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-02-02)

From East
(2024-02-02)

From South
(2024-02-02)

From West
(2024-02-02)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2024-02-02

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
Not available

39 – FRWILD – Freiburg Wildtal

Station location and siting

Station ID	FRWILD	Full name	Freiburg Wildtal
Latitude	48.0325°N	Longitude	7.892956°E
Topographic elevation	293.3 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Near Talstraße 131, 79194 Gundelfingen, Germany	Administrative unit	Municipality of Gundelfingen, District of Wildtal
Local Climate Zone	9 (Sparsely built)	Urban Atlas Class	23000
Sky view factor	0.679	Dominant land use	Agricultural (meadows and pastures)
Orographic setting	Valley	Artificial heat sources	None
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	50 m	Parking space:	40 m
		Tree:	17 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Meadows, pastures, lines of trees. E-W oriented small road with narrow sidewalk on side of station, very few scattered houses alongside, valley (sloping to the North-West) with mountains to the North-East and South, hill next to the Station to the North-East.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey light pole		Material	Metal
Height of structure	8 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.12 m	Light extension offset 0.3 m, $\alpha = 205^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.44 m, z = 3.21 m, $\alpha = 115^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.38 m, z = 3.09 m, $\alpha = 160^\circ$

History and remarks

History			Remarks
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-07-29	-	Pessl LoRain	

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2023-11-18)

From East
Not available

From South
(2023-11-18)

From West
Not available

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2023-11-18

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
2023-12-12

40 – FRWITT – Freiburg Wittnau

Station location and siting

Station ID	FRWITT	Full name	Freiburg Wittnau
Latitude	47.93786°N	Longitude	7.821302°E
Topographic elevation	443.6 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Near Sandbühl 20, 79299 Wittnau, Germany	Administrative unit	Municipality of Wittnau, district of Biezighofen
Local Climate Zone	9 (Sparsely built)	Urban Atlas Class	23000
Sky view factor	0.866	Dominant land use	Agricultural (meadows)
Orographic setting	North-facing slope	Artificial heat sources	None
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	12 m	Parking space:	None
		Tree:	40 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Hillside. Pastures and meadows, one small building to the North (water reservoir), scattered trees, forest edge approx. 100 m to the South-East.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey pole		Material	Metal
Height of structure	3.24 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.06 m	Light extension offset None
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.12 m, z = 3.24 m, $\alpha = 175^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.14 m, z = 3.10 m, $\alpha = 305^\circ$

History and remarks

History			Remarks
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-07-29	-	Pessl LoRain	

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2023-12-12)

From East
Not available

From South
(2023-12-12)

From West
Not available

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2023-12-12

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
2023-12-12

41 – FRWSEE – Freiburg Waldsee

Station location and siting

Station ID	FRWSEE	Full name	Freiburg Waldsee
Latitude	47.98597°N	Longitude	7.893637°E
Topographic elevation	315.3 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Steinackerstraße 22, 79117 Freiburg, Germany	Administrative unit	City of Freiburg, District of Waldsee
Local Climate Zone	6 (Open lowrise)	Urban Atlas Class	11210
Sky view factor	0.609	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Flat	Artificial heat sources	Cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	8 m	Parking space:	5 m
		Tree:	8 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
NE-SW oriented street with wide boardwalks, 2-3 storey detached residential buildings with front gardens.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey light pole		Material	Metal
Height of structure	7 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.1 m	Light extension offset 0.4 m, $\alpha = 290^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.42 m, z = 3.13 m, $\alpha = 150^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.36 m, z = 2.96 m, $\alpha = 180^\circ$

History and remarks

History			Remarks
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-04-07	-	Pessl LoRain	

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-02-21)

From East
(2024-02-21)

From South
(2024-02-21)

From West
(2024-02-21)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2024-02-21

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
Not available

42 – FRZAHR – Freiburg Zaehringen

Station location and siting

Station ID	FRZAHR	Full name	Freiburg Zaehringen
Latitude	48.0205°N	Longitude	7.866976°E
Topographic elevation	276.8 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Schlehenrain 11, 79108 Freiburg, Germany	Administrative unit	City of Freiburg, District of Zähringen
Local Climate Zone	6 (Open lowrise)	Urban Atlas Class	11210
Sky view factor	0.654	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Slope	Artificial heat sources	Cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	10 m	Parking space:	1.5 m
		Tree:	2 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
N-S oriented street with sidewalk on both sides, curbside car parking, 2-3 storey, detached houses with large gardens, scattered trees and hedges; slight slope falling to the North-East.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey light pole		Material	Metal
Height of structure	4.5 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.07 m	Light extension offset 0.3 m, $\alpha = 90^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.41 m, z = 3.08 m, $\alpha = 180^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.35 m, z = 2.96 m, $\alpha = 210^\circ$

History and remarks

History			Remarks
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2022-04-05	-	Pessl LoRain	

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2023-11-18)

From East
Not available

From South
Not available

From West
(2023-11-18)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
2023-11-18

Panoramic photographs
From top of rain gauge
2024-01-19

